

Banana peels as alternative for chemical components in making mosquito repellent

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Abstract

Philippines is one of the countries that are prone to diseases caused by mosquitoes. In fact, many Filipinos' death has been caused by diseases like "Dengue" and "Malaria". The researchers have thought of a way where we would not spend that much money in making other commercialized mosquito repellents and take the risk of destroying our environment and causing the increasing of pollution in the country. The researchers thought that a great component in making these mosquito repellents should be one of the wastes that we have not yet acknowledged. When we eat bananas, we usually just end up throwing the peels away after eating. But the researchers want to know if banana peels can be a component in making a mosquito repellent. Through this, they can hit 'two birds with one stone' by making a mosquito repellent out of something that is one of the wastes in our country. For the researchers to make a banana mosquito repellent, they will first collect the banana peels and dry them. After drying, they will then extract the essential oils from the banana peels using various ways such as using a blender, mortar and pestle, and ethanol. Through this, they can extract the essential oils and find out if banana mosquito repellent is effective and can be a substitute for commercialized mosquito repellent, and if banana peels extract can work with other mosquito-repelling plants in repelling mosquitoes. The researchers found out that the banana mosquito repellent is actually an effective substitute to commercialized mosquito repellents and that they can combine it with other mosquito-repelling plants in making mosquito repellents to enhance its effectivity. If given more time, the researchers would effectively explore other ways in researching this study.

Keywords: Banana peels; Chemical components; Mosquito repellent; Dengue; Malaria.

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To cite this article:

Selosa, A. A. D., Atienza, J. K., Apostol, R. H., Cas, J. C., Ramboanga, S. G., & Salvador, K. M. (2021). Banana peels as alternative for chemical components in making mosquito repellent. *SDCA Student Research Journal*, 10(1), 6-9.

Introduction

Mosquito repellents are substances/chemicals used to control the growing number of mosquitoes by killing them and preventing them from undesirable or destructive behaviors. Repellents act upon the nervous system of the mosquito (e.g., cholinesterase (Ch.E.) inhibition). Repellents are commonly used in public health, household and commercial uses.

On the other side, *Musa acuminata* is part of species of wild banana native to Southeast Asia. It belongs to section *Musa* of the genus *Musa*.

The country is experiencing many hardships and problems. Some of which being a big problem to us in terms of health. Throughout the years, numbers and numbers of cases about the dangers that mosquitoes can bring to people are popping up. Examples of them are the infamous diseases called "Dengue" and "Malaria".

Bringing harm to many Filipinos in many areas. Not only that, but the country is also experiencing problems that discipline about cleanliness and proper disposals. To be specific, "bananas". After eating them, there is really not much of use for them.

In this case, the researchers are motivated to find out the use of banana peel extract as a main solution for alternative repellent for the public.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to test the effectiveness of the banana peels extract in repelling mosquitoes. Especially, to answer the following questions:

1. Is the extract of the banana peel effective in repelling mosquitoes?
2. What is the best extraction method to obtain the essential oil from banana peels?
3. Will the banana peel essential oil work with other mosquito-repelling plants?
4. Which mosquito repellent is the most and least effective?
5. What substance in the banana mosquito repellent is the cause of repelling mosquito?

Significance of the Study

To the barangay. The study could be significant to the barangay since it could help lessen the mosquitoes that lay their eggs on water reservoirs and sewages to grow their population. These mosquitoes are mostly the reason of the occurrence of various illnesses caused by the mosquitoes.

To the city. The study could be significant to the city in times of shortage of budget for providing medicines and remedies for people who get sickness from mosquitoes, the banana mosquito repellent would be a great substitute for those.

To the country. The study could be significant to the country in times of diseases being viral due to the country's climate. The banana mosquito repellent would help when a disease carried by mosquitoes would be present.

To the environment. The study could be significant to the environment to help reduce wastes including banana peels that contributes to pollution. The banana mosquito repellent would make great use of these residuals.

Scope and Delimitation

This study is limited on pertaining to know the effectiveness of using banana peels as a main component in making mosquito repellents. This intends to use banana in replace for chemical components in making mosquito repellents.

This study is limited on the number of times experiments are going to be done. In doing the experiment, (1) Prepare materials needed for the experiments including the main component, banana; (2) Extract essential oils (Octenol) from banana peels; (3) With the essential oils ready, make the product. For that, the researchers are going to use instruments or materials like jars. This study is conducted in the Facility of Research Laboratory from July 24, 2019 to January 30, 2020.

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formed in the research study:

1. If only banana peel essential oil is in the mosquito repellent, then there would be no mosquitoes repelled.
2. Mortar and pestle would be the most efficient method in extracting banana mosquito repellent.
3. If the banana peel essential oil is to be mixed with other mosquito-repelling plants, then it would repel mosquitoes.
4. Banana with garlic mosquito repellent would be the most effective mosquito repellent.
5. The banana essential oil "Octenol" would be the cause of repellence of mosquitoes.

Methodology

Sampling Technique

There are about four types of banana grown here in the Philippines: Lakatan, Latundan, Bungulan, and Saba. Having all of them used in the study could cost a lot and consume much time, thus the researchers picked their samples based on the convenience of their place and budget. The researchers took a sample which is Lakatan by using the convenience sampling technique. The researchers collected 10 samples of Lakatan banana for their research study.

A. Collection of Banana Peels

Collect 10 bananas from your desired market. Separate the peel from the inside of the banana. Air dry the banana peels to be ready for extraction.

B. Extraction of Essential Oil "Octenol" from Banana Peels

There are three (3) ways we will use in extracting essential oils from banana peels:

First, the way where we blend the banana peels to extract the octenol from it. To do that, ready the container with the banana peels in. Put the banana peels in the blender and blend it. A mushy banana peel will be the result and use a strainer to get only the juices from it because it will contain the essential oil "Octenol."

Second, the way of using mortar and pestle to extract octenol from banana peels. To do that, ready the container with the banana peels in. Put the banana peels in little by little. Then pestle the banana peels and get the juices out of it. Those juices may contain octenol and may be used in making the mosquito repellent.

Third is by using ethanol and this time with garlic and lemongrass. Cut the bananas and lemongrass to strips, pinch the garlic into small cloves. Prepare three (3) jars and for the jars, put bananas, bananas and cloves of garlics, bananas and lemongrass. For each jar, pour ethanol only up to when the bananas are an inch below the top of the ethanol. Leave the jars for a few days, shake the jar each day. Filter out the essential oils from each jar.

Figure 1. Process diagram

Table 1. Ratio of the components in each mosquito repellent

Product	Ratio
Banana Mosquito Repellent	3:2 (Ethanol : Banana)
Banana with Lemongrass Mosquito Repellent	3:1:1 (Ethanol : Lemongrass : Banana)
Banana with Garlic Mosquito Repellent	3:2:1 (Ethanol : Garlic : Banana)

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Effectiveness of each mosquito repellent

Mosquito Repellent	Is it effective?	
	Yes	No
Banana Mosquito Repellent	/	
Banana with Lemongrass Mosquito Repellent	/	
Banana with Garlic Mosquito Repellent	/	

In Table 2, all of the mosquito repellents are effective in repelling mosquitoes. As the researchers test the products in a cage with mosquitoes, not even one mosquito tried to go to the object that was sprayed with the products.

Effectiveness

Figure 2. Effectiveness of each mosquito repellent

As seen in Figure 2, the banana with garlic mosquito repellent has the highest effectiveness rate in repelling mosquitoes while the banana with lemongrass mosquito repellent comes before it and the banana mosquito repellent comes in last.

Table 3. Results of phytochemical screening

Phytochemical Tests	Observation	Inferences
Tannins Test	Dark yellow orange	+
Froth Test	No foam is observed	-
Carbohydrates and Glycosides Test	Dirty brown	-
Flavonoids Test	Clear	-

In Table 3, the only positive result is the Tannins Test, meaning Tannin is present in the banana mosquito repellent. Tannin is a substance that can poison insects. Tannin would be the substance for the reason why mosquitoes are being repelled.

Figure 3. Phytochemical test results

Conclusions

After the researchers tested about the mosquito repellent products, they have concluded that banana mosquito repellent is a good mosquito repellent. Ethanol extraction method is the most efficient method to extract banana peel essential oils. Banana peel extract can work with other mosquito-repelling plants to repel mosquitoes. Banana with Garlic is the most effective mosquito repellent followed by Banana with Lemongrass mosquito repellent, and Banana mosquito repellent is the least effective among the tested mosquito repellents. The substance found in the banana mosquito repellent that causes the repellence of mosquito is Tannin.

Recommendations

After conducting this research study, the researchers recommend that conclusions were made with the help of simple experiments. Doing more tests in the mosquito repellent is recommended. The researchers recommend using advance equipment in extracting essential oil from the banana peels. The researchers recommend combining other mosquito-repelling plants like lavender to find out its effectiveness in repelling mosquitoes. The results show the effectiveness of each repellent thus combining lemongrass, garlic, and banana peel's essential oil for a wide range of effectivity is recommended. The researcher recommends going through more testing of the banana peel's essential oil.

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